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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

We are again thrilled to announce our current publication of Volume 8, Issue 1- May 2024. Within the academic and scientific journey of consistency publication have gained multiple experiences with the authors and reviewers, which the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) will always appreciate and have learned to move extra miles. Moreover, sometimes, there are authors whose submission may not have been accepted either during the editorial review and in the initial screening phase or by the reviewers, we also highly appreciate those authors for considering JIS for publication platform.

A journey in research is not always simple and there are multiple issues that relates to inconsistency in scientific and academic realm, however, JIS is determined in promoting to enrich the beautiful minds and towards intelligent minds, for which authors whose articles were not accepted on any of the occasions, we are here to help to create an avenue if scientific and academic construction are further developed of those articles. We are also creating open access platform for the readers offering free download of current and archived articles, although, the JIS is a social contributor and receives no funding from any other organization, the editor is solely supporting the JIS for being academically responsible for the authors, readers, scientists, researchers, students and to all around the globe for academic enrichment. JIS proudly stand to appreciate all the authors so far who have trusted JIS and have published their articles during the journey from 2017 to 2024.

Our next issue will be published in November 2024 and we invite researchers, managers, leaders, scientists, students and others for paper submission. The call for paper submission is also announced in the journal's announcement portal

<http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/announcement/>

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It is recommended that all author(s) submitting their manuscript to JIS are advised to read the author guidelines from the journal website

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Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
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Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
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